

Classification for Brain Computer Interfaces by Machine Learning Methods

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According to the Association for the Promotion of Paraplegics, 140,000 people with such a disability live in Germany (as of 2021) [2], including many with paraplegia at the level of the cervical spine. As a result, they are limited in their movement and motor skills in everyday life. However, there is hope. In 2006, thanks to an investment in advancing technology, one subject was able to learn how to open email or move a robotic arm with his mind. This was possible through the implementation of micro-electrodes and the Brain Computer Interface (BCI). [5]

This Brain Computer Interface is an information interface between the brain and a technical device. With the help of recordings of brain signals, the Brain Computer Interface can be used to control various devices or execute commands, such as controlling a cursor or spelling with the help of thoughts. In both medical and non-medical fields (such as gaming), BCI is gaining popularity and taking an important role in today's society. [1, 3, 4]

The implementation of such a brain interface is done in three steps: signal collection, signal processing and output device. First, the signals are collected. This is possible in two different ways, by surgical or non-surgical intervention. Surgically, microelectrodes are implemented directly on the brain, thus more accurate signals (without noise) can be collected. However, the insertion of such an implant carries a high risk, as the electrodes are placed directly on the brain. The second way to collect data is without a surgical procedure. For example, electroencephalography (EEG) can be used to collect information from brain signals, and the electrodes are placed on the head. Brain activity can then be recorded based on voltage

alternations between pairs of electrodes. After the signal information is collected, the signals go through further steps in signal processing. First, the signals must be cleaned of noise and artifacts by filtering. This allows features to be extracted from the signals, such as frequencies or voltages. In the last step of signal processing, the features are classified by means of an algorithm in such a way that a correct command to the technical devices such as a robot arm can be executed or a letter can be classified on the basis of brain signals. [1, 3]

In order to implement the classification in signal processing, a wide variety of machine learning techniques can be used for this step. In their work, Hongchang and Todor showed a comparison between classifications with traditional models, for example, SVM or decision trees and Deep Learning techniques such as the Convolutional Neural Network [7]. Using the techniques, visual perception should be classified based on the EEG data of eleven passers-by. Their brain signals should be used to identify the frequency with which an image appears and disappears. [3]

The classifications with traditional models did not provide a convincing result with a mean accuracy between 45% and 65%. Among the traditional techniques, SVM with a Gaussian kernel and sequential forward selection set was one of the better performing classification techniques with a mean accuracy of 66.09%. The CNN achieved an even better result with a mean accuracy of 69.03%. Here, the CNN consisted of five layers strung together: Input, convolution, ReLU, pooling, and a fully connected layer. [7]

However, there is not only one particular constructed CNN for a good classification. That's

what one team is finding in their work. They show that a wide variety of neural networks can be used to analyze non surgical brain signals in order to correctly classify letters in their application, for example. For this comparison, they use complex neural networks, such as a CNN consisting of three convolutional layers and three fully-connected layers with dropout or pooling function or a Convolutional Neural Network including five layers with additional batch normalize and dropout functions. These networks contain parameter counts from 37,502 up to 21,950,818 parameters. The models were contrasted with one of the simplest constructed CNN: One Convolution Layer Neural Network. This is a single layer CNN consisting of only two layers in total, the convolution layer with dropout function and the output layer. On the basis of the parameter number of the model with 16,882 it confirms again that it is, in comparison to the others, a very simple neural network.

The simple model can classify the correct letter with an accuracy of 92.41% for one of the data sets used for testing. In comparison, the more complex networks were a little less accurate, but still achieved accuracies of about 84% to 86%. [4]

It turns out that even with simple, classifications with traditional models, brain signals can be analyzed and classified. However, if one attaches much importance to a high accuracy rate, which is necessary in medical applications, various other machine learning methods should be applied. It should be noted that complexities of a neural network do not automatically have to have a positive influence on the accuracy of the classifications. [4, 7]

It is not only the different techniques used for analysis and feature extractions that can have an impact on classification accuracy. The nature of the brain signal recordings themselves also plays an important role. Non-surgical sources such as EEG, while a low-cost and hazard-free alternative to capture brain signals, contain very high levels of noise, which can negatively affect classification accuracy. Surgical interventions, on the other hand, pro-

vide more accurate and easier-to-analyze data, but involve a high cost and risk in preparation to be able to record the information. [1, 5] However, both variants have the same challenge. The brain data of a person can lead to very good classifications in the person's very own perspective. If you use the same training data set on another person, the classification may not work well because the brain signals of the two people may be different and may differ from each other. Generalization from such models is not completely ruled out, but is a challenge that can be mitigated by other models such as LSTM or calibration.[6, 8]

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